

SCOIR Funder Open Access Policy Guidelines Report

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Title	SCOIR Funder Open Access Policy Guidelines Report			
Description	<p>The SCOIR project is two-year project (2023-2025) funded by the National Open Research Forum (NORF). SCOIR aims to support the goal of 100% open access to publicly-funded research publications by adopting a two-pronged approach to policy and legislative change:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Develop a secondary publishing right for Ireland, drafting legislation in support of secondary publication rights based on an analysis of international and Irish law.2. Develop an open access policy framework for both funders and institutions that is aligned with the National Action Plan for Open Research and international best practice. <p>The project is jointly led by Trinity College Dublin and Technological University Dublin and is supported by a consortium of a wide range of partners and affiliates along with an international advisory board. This document is an outcome of (2) above.</p>			
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Executive Summary

This report describes the creation of funder policy guidelines in fulfilment of the SCOIR project's objective of creating a model open access policy aligned with the Irish policy landscape. Following extensive consultation with project partners, it was decided to create policy guidelines rather than a model policy. The purpose of this report is primarily to document the rationale behind the contents of the policy and explain why decisions were taken, but secondarily to provide this background as guidance for successful approval and implementation of these policy guidelines. This report also provides an explanation for why it has not been necessary to include a rights retention component to this policy.

Background

SCOIR stands for Secondary rights, Copyright, Open access, Institutional policies, and Rights retention. This project aimed to achieve the objectives outlined by NORF by drafting secondary rights legislation for Ireland and by creating an Open Access and Rights Retention policy framework for institutions and funders. The potential impact of secondary rights legislation on funder policies is being considered alongside the existing policy landscape and the recommendations of the National Action Plan for Open Research,

National Open Research Landscape Report and the Copyright Legislation to Support Rights Retention Policy Brief.¹

This report addresses the project objective of ‘Create an OA policy framework aligned with the Irish policy landscape’ and describes the output ‘Updated, NORF-aligned, funder OA policy for Irish research funding organisations.’ The aim of the project is to create model policy for Irish research funding organisations which can be adopted in a wide range of local contexts.

The original project proposal included a deliverable of a model funder open access policy. Following extensive discussions with the funders involved in SCOIR and due to funders own operational circumstances, it was decided to create policy guidelines rather than a policy to accommodate the different phases of updates that funders have to their own open access policies. The project acknowledges that not all funders may be able to adopt wholesale these guidelines however it is intended that they will be used to inform future policy development across Irish funders. This report and the policy guidelines themselves present a rationale and strong recommendation for policy developments going forward.

Methodology

Timeframe

The guidelines were developed throughout 2024 and early 2025. There were three draft versions and a final version was created in March 2025. All versions are available to view on Zenodo.²

Stakeholders

A funder subgroup, including representatives from Health Research Board, Taighde Éireann and the Environmental Protection Agency was set up to discuss developing the policy. This group concluded that policy guidelines would be more appropriate due to various stages of policy development within their organisations.

Policy review

The major Irish funder open access policies were reviewed including Science Foundation Ireland, Irish Research Council, Health Research Board and the Environmental Protection Agency along with the European Commission's open access policy for Horizon Europe. It was not possible to locate public versions of other Irish funders' open access policies. The main findings of the analysis were the divergence between Coalition S member funders and others in the areas of copyright retention, repository deposit and embargoes. Most funders also restrict the open access policy to peer reviewed publications only but this was omitted in acknowledgment of the wide array of research publications which can be funded.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.ff36jz222>, <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.5q485c938>, <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.jd47gm74p>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15114307>

Guidelines

In light of the expectation of aligning the policy with Plan S and the parallel developments of the institutional policy and draft legislation, the work package took the decision to create the guidelines based on the institutional policy because it would ensure alignment with the model institutional policy and the draft legislation. These guidelines are heavily informed by Plan S but they do diverge slightly from it in some areas, and these variations and rationale are highlighted in the report below.

The guidelines are broken up into sections as a policy would be. It is attempted to make them as detailed as possible and as implementable as possible in a policy format.

Purpose

The policy begins with a statement of purpose followed by the scope section. This is in keeping with the policy frameworks which were used to develop the model institutional policies and also reflected a similar format to many funder policies.³

Scope

The suggested scope is broader than any funder policies at present in that it applies to all kinds of research publications arising from grant funding including books and book chapters, reflecting the ambition from the National Action Plan for Open Research of 100% open access to research publications.⁴ Earlier versions of the guidelines included language to clarify the status of a research publication as opposed to a creative work or other type of publication. However it was felt that this could be omitted since funders can determine whether the work they are funding is research or not. This policy does not restrict its scope to peer reviewed publications only, however it is acknowledged that some funders may choose to apply that restriction.

Rationale

The rationale section outlines synergies between the policy and external initiatives including Plan S, UNESCO Recommendations on Open Science amongst others.⁵ The rationale section also expands on the purpose section by outlining the reasons for adopting an open access policy.

Actions

The main body of the policy guidelines covers the actions required. The first of these is a recognition of the funder's endorsement of the National Action Plan for Open Research. The other action is a requirement for those in receipt of grant funding to make their publications open access and to deposit them in an open repository. A requirement to deposit in an open

³ <https://open-access.network/en/information/policy-frameworks/open-access-policies>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.ff36jz222>

⁵ <https://www.coalition-s.org/>, <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/about>

repository regardless of whether the publication is made open access with a publisher is new to Irish funder policies and represents a divergence from Plan S.⁶ It was felt important to align with the institutional policy developed by SCOIR. While many funders encourage repository deposit, making it a requirement is thought to help to ensure the preservation of the scholarly record and provide robustness in making publications open access and ensuring they remain open access. The term 'open repository' is defined in the guidelines. It was deemed necessary to use a specific term to highlight an enhanced level of trust and curation from a repository.

Earlier versions of the guidelines contained a lot of detail around exceptions and limitations to these requirements based on language from the draft legislation. These details were subsequently removed on the basis that this could be covered under implementation rather than in the policy itself. Funders have established processes for managing such requests which could be utilised for this purpose.

The group included that the policy should contain a statement that the researcher is encouraged to retain copyright to their research publications. This is presented as a requirement by Plan S however this guideline adds that the open access version must be published under a Creative Commons license which we believe has the same effect as requiring retention of copyright. It has also been noted that some funders in other countries have had difficulty in implementing a requirement for authors to retain copyright in all research publications.

In common with the institutional policy, the guidelines recommend including a requirement to include a data availability statement on any research publication including where there is no underlying data, software or code. This is in keeping with many publisher policies and promotes another ambition of the National Action Plan for Open Research, enabling FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) research data and other outputs. Some funders are also considering including a recommendation for ethics statements to be included also.

It was suggested to add a point promoting making preprints open access. This is not included in the institutional policy but aligns with Plan S which includes similar encouragement and the use of a Creative Commons Attribution licence when making preprints available.

Implementation Guidelines

Following feedback from the partners that certain sections of the policy guidelines contained too much detail around implementation, a section for this purpose was created. It was agreed that there should be some acknowledgement of services that funders may provide to support open access to publications, including the provision of systems, e.g. a publishing platform, or persistent identifier infrastructure. While funders can influence researchers' behaviour through policy, it is also useful to note the investment funders contribute to the environment of open access and open research.

⁶ https://www.coalition-s.org/plan_s_principles/

Similarly, a commitment to monitoring and measuring compliance with the policy was deemed important to include in the guidelines to ensure that there is accountability for researchers' compliance with the policy.

Providing more detail on how outputs can be made open access, the policy should allow for open access publication via green, gold or diamond routes. It is important that all routes to publication are supported in recognition of the existing infrastructure and publishing environment, which supports all of these routes to open access, as well as the ambition of the National Action Plan and the European Commission to support and develop diamond open access publishing routes.

Linked with this, and providing more detail on the conditions under which an output can be made open access, the guidelines recommend that the output be made openly available under a Creative Commons Attribution licence, unless there is a legitimate reason to use another Creative Commons licence. This is a slight variation from Plan S, which only allows Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike or Creative Commons Attribution-No Derivatives licenses to be applied as an exception.⁷ Similarly, where an output cannot be made open access, the author in receipt of grant funding would need to apply to the funder for an exemption. Further detail of how this could be managed is left to the discretion of the funders themselves.

Date and review period

It is suggested that this policy be reviewed regularly, at least every five years, and should be updated in light of the current landscape. A full glossary is also provided with the policy.

Exclusions

Similar to the institutional policy developed by SCOIR, it was decided that rights retention language, such as that promoted by Plan S, was not necessary as an author's accepted manuscript version of a publication can be deposited in a repository with no infringement on publisher copyrights.

In contrast to the model institutional policy, these guidelines do not contain a proviso stating a respect for the right of researchers to publish wherever they deem most appropriate. This statement was not deemed relevant in the context of funder policies, as funders seek to influence researcher behaviour with the terms and conditions of their funding.

Conclusion

These policy guidelines provide a basis for policies that support the goal of achieving 100% open access to research publications in Ireland. While heavily informed by Plan S, they do not include a rights retention requirement as the project has determined it is not necessary in the Irish legal context. These guidelines are intended to be practical and widely adoptable,

⁷ <https://www.coalition-s.org/guidance-on-the-implementation-of-plan-s/>

but the project acknowledges that some funders may need to adapt the policy to fit their local structures.

Next steps

The project is working on creating a suite of guidance materials to support institutions to review their policies and to understand the implications of the draft legislation if it is enacted.

Adoption ambitions

The ambition is for these guidelines to inform the redevelopment of funder open access policies. Details of the status of the partner funder open access policies is provided below.

Taighde Éireann - Research Ireland	Research Ireland will publish an interim Open Research policy shortly, which was created based on these guidelines with some variations. An updated Open Research policy is intended to be produced later in 2025 and will bring Research Ireland's policy into even closer alignment with these guidelines.
Health Research Board	Since 1 January 2025, the Health Research Board has adopted an open access policy aligned with Plan S.
Environmental Protection Agency	The EPA's Open Access policy will be updated and closely based on these guidelines
Marine Institute	Marine Institute currently do not have a specific Funder Open Access Policy and hope to adopt and approve a new one based on this model policy